

DELIVERABLE

D.2.1.3. – IDENTIFICATION OF GAP OF KNOWLEDGE REGARDING MISSING/NOT VALIDATED INDICATORS, LAYING HENS WELFARE IN ALTERNATIVE HOUSING SYSTEMS.

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1. Introduction

This document is part of the sub-activity 2.1 “*Relevant animal welfare indicators*” and concerns to the priority area related to the laying hens welfare in alternative housing systems. Here, the possible gaps of knowledge and ‘open norms’ are identified and discussed.

2. Methodology used

The information has been retrieved from questionnaires sent to the Competent Authorities (CAs) or from workshops that had taken place during a meeting between EURCAW-Poultry-SFA and Competent Authorities in September 2020 in Nice (France): laying hens welfare in alternative housing systems.

Definitions

Legal requirement: a requisite of the EU legislation to be assessed during the official controls.

Example: Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10: “*Temperature, relative air humidity [...] must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals*”

Gap of knowledge: lack of technical and scientific information about the validity, reliability or feasibility of the indicators or its method.

Example: absence of knowledge about how to assess the rate of dust in a barn.

Open-norms: requirement in the EU legislation which does not unambiguously translate into qualitative or quantitative criteria that can be used to check/verify compliance.

Example: dust level

3. Gaps of knowledge and open norms on laying hens welfare in alternative housing systems

3.1. Legal Requirement: “*The stocking density must not exceed 9 laying hens per m² usable area.*” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Article 4)

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.2. Legal Requirement: “*The floors of installations must be constructed so as to support adequately each of the forward-facing claws of each foot.*” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Article 4)

There is a lack of information to determine what kind of installations is appropriate and what is adequate.

3.3. Legal Requirement: “[...] *dust levels must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals*” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Point 10)

In the legal requirement, there is no threshold for dust level and no definition of what is harmful to the animals. Competent Authorities express difficulties concerning this requirement mainly linked to the absence of threshold, the lack of an objective indicator and method of assessment. There is no known indicator based on hens’ behaviour linked to dust level but some studies show negative health effects like lung lesions in laying hens, broiler chickens and turkeys (David et al., 2015b). These effects could be amplified by hot

temperatures because panting (mouth-breathing) allows the dust to penetrate deeper into the respiratory system. Nevertheless, this indicator is not usable on farm inspection (rather with post mortem analysis). There is no scientific knowledge on what level of dust could be considered as harmful to poultry or what frequency of respiratory trouble could be considered as problematic. Additionally, devices to measure dust levels are underused, since it is needed to leave them on-site for hours for the sampling. Hence there are no standardized thresholds nor guidelines. It seems to be possible to use low-cost sensors to evaluate particulate matter in farm as it is already been used (Yasmeen et al., 2019) but it would be interesting to test these low-cost sensors in depth. Particularly, we need more investigations on their accuracy.

3.4. Legal Requirement: *“All systems must be equipped in such a way that all laying hens have: (a) either linear feeders providing at least 10 cm per bird or circular feeders providing at least 4 cm per bird” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Article 4)*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.5. Legal Requirement: *“(…) (b) either continuous drinking troughs providing 2.5 cm per hen or circular drinking troughs providing 1 cm per hen. In addition, where nipple drinkers or cups are used, there shall be at least one nipple drinker or cup for every 10 hens. Where drinking points are plumbed in, at least two cups or two nipple drinkers shall be within reach of each hen” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Article 4)*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.6. Legal Requirement: *“[...]gas concentrations must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Point 10)*

Competent Authorities have put in evidence the lack of knowledge about the gas levels that could be harmful for the animals as one of their main difficulties. They also have concern about the lack of threshold concerning this requirement. Indeed, in absence of concrete legal threshold, Competent Authority could have problem to take action except when the gas levels are really high.

ABIs described in the deliverable **D2.1.1** (irritation of mucus membrane, air sac lesions, keratoconjunctivitis and lungs lesions) are not described in this document because they are not specific and/or feasible on farm inspection. These indicators are used in some scientific papers on the physiological (and sometimes behavioural) impacts in poultry of high ammonia levels (research on carbon dioxide is scarcer) but they are not relevant for the assessment of the compliance with this requirement. Ammonia levels have negative impacts on mucus membranes (irritation), food intake and weight loss, air sac (lesions) and can cause keratoconjunctivitis (from 20 ppm) (David et al., 2015a; Kristensen et al., 2000; Ritz et al., 2004) but these indicators are not usable on farm inspection, but rather for post mortem examination, or cannot be specifically linked to ammonia level in air.

Kristensen and colleagues (2000) showed that atmospheric ammonia was aversive to laying hens at a level between 0 and 25 ppm. And Jones and colleagues (2005) had found that broilers avoid ammonia concentrations of 20 and 37 ppm when they can, and preferred 4, 11 or 12 ppm levels (they spent more time at 4 ppm).

3.7. Legal Requirement: *“All buildings shall have light levels sufficient to allow all hens to see one another and be seen clearly, to investigate their surroundings visually and to show normal*

levels of activity. After the first days of conditioning, the lighting regime shall be such as to prevent health and behavioural problems. Accordingly it must follow a 24-hour rhythm and include an adequate uninterrupted period of darkness lasting, by way of indication, about one third of the day, so that the hens may rest and to avoid problems such as immunodepression and ocular anomalies.” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Annex, point 3)

Competent Authorities put in evidence that the lack of legal norms for this requirement (“sufficient” intensity or “adequate” uninterrupted period of darkness) could lead to subjective assessment. Some of them point the lack of objective indicator to assess the compliance with this requirement. Indeed, a lot of them use light program records but in some farms, there is no lighting program records.

In this requirement, there is no definition of “sufficient” and which threshold can be used during inspection to evaluate the light intensity. Light intensity needs to be set depending on animals’ age and breed. Young layers (and broilers) of two weeks old prefer high light intensity (200 lux) but this preference disappears few weeks later (Davis et al., 1999). At 6 weeks old, layers (and broilers) spend more time in dimmest environment (<10 lux) but this preference is only associated with two behaviours: resting and perching. There are, also, some studies on type of light preferences. Laying hens and pullets prefer fluorescent lights (2700 K) than LED (2000 K) and incandescent lights (Widowski et al. 1992 in (Gunnarsson and Hermansson, 2011); (Liu et al., 2017)). Long and colleagues (2016) showed different impacts on laying hens rearing with fluorescent lighting and light-emitting diode (LED) lighting. Under LED lighting, hens tend to have poorer plumage condition and insulation than under fluorescent lighting. The authors have alluded that LED lights could impact feather conditions (and hens’ behaviours) differently depending on the breeds. In addition, according to the authors, hens seem to be more alert at 36 weeks (but not at 60 weeks) when reared under LED lighting than under fluorescent lighting (larger median avoidance distance).

3.8. Legal Requirement: *“A period of twilight of sufficient duration ought to be provided when the light is dimmed so that the hens may settle down without disturbance or injury.” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Annex, Paragraph 3)*

One Competent Authority has indicated as a trouble that there is no definition of twilight. The lack of threshold is also highlighted by the Competent Authorities.

There is limited information in literature about what is a sufficient duration of twilight, but recommendations exist. EFSA (2005) recommended between 5 and 10 minutes of twilight duration for cage systems and between 15 and 30 minutes for non-cage systems to allow the hens to settle down and avoid disturbance and injury. And French Competent Authority in their methodology for broilers (DGAL/SDSPA/2017-998) indicates that twilight period needs to last during at least 30 minutes to avoid stress factors (less activity, less competition to reach the feeders,...).

3.9. Legal Requirement: *“Where there is natural light, light apertures must be arranged in such a way that light is distributed evenly within the accommodation.” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Annex, Paragraph 3)*

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.10. Legal Requirement: “[...] temperature, relative air humidity [...] must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Point 10)

Competent Authorities have indicated the lack of knowledge about the temperature and relative humidity that could be harmful for the animals as a difficulty to assess the compliance with this requirement. According to ICFAW (2017), optimal temperatures for laying hens are between 21 and 22°C but the temperatures are comfortably tolerated between 10 and 27°C. They also have concern about the vague limits and the lack of threshold concerning this requirement. Without threshold, the judgement could be subjective. For example, it would be up to Competent Authorities Inspectors to decide the thresholds of animals panting or huddling that are not acceptable. In addition, they indicate the lack of specific indicator and method of assessment of relative humidity as difficulties.

3.11. Legal Requirement: “Ventilation shall be sufficient to avoid overheating and, where necessary in combination with heating systems to remove excessive moisture” (Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Point 10)

There is a lack of definition concerning “excessive moisture”. Competent Authorities raise concern about the vague limits and the lack of threshold concerning this requirement. They put in evidence, for example, the absence of moisture parameters defined. Without threshold, the judgement could be subjective. In addition, they indicate the lack of specific indicator and method of assessment of ventilation as problematic.

3.12. Legal Requirement: “At least one nest for every seven hens. If group nests are used, there must be at least 1 m² of nest space for a maximum of 120 hens” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Article 4)

There are no gaps of knowledge or open norms for this requirement.

3.13. Legal Requirement: “Adequate perches, without sharp edges and providing at least 15 cm per hen. Perches must not be mounted above the litter and the horizontal distance between perches must be at least 30 cm and the horizontal distance between the perch and the wall must be at least 20 cm” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Article 4)

There is a lack of definition in the directive of what is an “adequate” perch. EFSA report (2015) indicates that hens show a preference for perches higher than 60 cm for night-time roosting and between 3 and 6 cm of perch width is recommended. EFSA also specifies that the risk of injuries increases when hens have to jump distance of more than 80 cm (vertically, horizontally or diagonally) or jump an angle between 45 and 90° (measured at the horizontal level).

3.14. Legal Requirement: “At least 250 cm² of littered area per hen, the litter occupying at least one third of the ground surface” (Directive 1999/74/EC, Article 4).

Some points could be problematic for Competent Authorities like dry droppings substrate considered or not as litter. Another problem is the way to count littered area and perches, CAs have sometimes trouble to know what to do if perches are above littered area. In the perch definition in the directive, a perch should not be above the litter. One Competent Authority indicated that there are usually perches above litter and in most of the case, the surface underneath the perches is not count as littered area.

3.15. Legal Requirement: *“In addition to the provisions laid down in points 1 and 2, (a) if systems of rearing are used where the laying hens can move freely between different levels, (i) there shall be no more than four levels; (ii) the headroom between the levels must be at least 45 cm; (iii) the drinking and feeding facilities must be distributed in such a way as to provide equal access for all hens; (iv) the levels must be so arranged as to prevent droppings falling on the levels below.”* (Directive 1999/74/EC, Article 4)

The lack of definition of what is a level could be problematic. Indeed, the requirement says that there shall not be more than 4 levels, but it is unclear if the floor is counted as a level or not. It is particularly important to know for aviaries systems.

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